

EVALUATION OF EFFECTIVENESS OF REHABILITATION METHODS IN OSTEOARTHRITIS

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Resume. This article aims to study the dynamics of results with important features describing the course of the disease in patients with osteoarthritis using the rehabilitation measures recommended by us , to conduct a comparative analysis and to determine the factors that determine the effectiveness of rehabilitation methods.

Keywords: rheumatic diseases, disability, osteoarthrosis, rehabilitation, sprain, knee, obesity, medical exercises, gonarthrosis, coxarthrosis.

Relevance. Osteoarthritis of the joint is a common form of joint pathology, which accounts for 60-70% of all rheumatic diseases. As a person ages, the incidence of OA increases significantly. Thus, osteoarthrosis occurs in only 3-5% of patients under the age of 45, in 30% between the ages of 45 and 64, and in 60-70% of patients over the age of 65. Arthrosis of the knee joints is most common in 10% of the population over 55 years of age, and in 25% of cases there are clear signs of functional activity. The basis of the disease is damage to all components of the joint: cartilage, subchondral bone, synovial shell, tendons, periarticular muscles, and it is manifested by pain and limitation of movements in the joint.

According to an epidemiological review (Johnson and Hunter 2014), the incidence and prevalence of osteoarthritis is increasing rapidly as a result of population aging and increased life expectancy. However, the current treatment provided by clinicians to patients with osteoarthritis is limited to symptom

management (Correa and Lietman 2017; DeRogatis et al. 2019), which cannot halt the progression of the condition.

According to the latest information, arthrosis is classified as a group of multifactorial diseases caused by the complex effects of internal and external causes. The 2017 clinical guidelines state: "Osteoarthritis (OA) (according to the international classification, osteoarthritis) is a heterogeneous group of diseases of different etiologies with biological, morphological, clinical manifestations, affecting all components of the joint, primarily the cartilage, as well as subchondral bone, synovial based on damage to the membrane, ligaments, capsule, periarticular muscles" .

In the analysis of the literature, it is highlighted that at the current stage of the treatment of osteoarthritis in the stage of medical rehabilitation, this problem has been studied in different directions and specific aspects. However, it has been found that this is a difficult problem and there is no general consensus on the treatment system. With this in mind, we believe that it is correct to study the effect of medical factors in relation to the level of joint pain and inflammation. In research and in the rehabilitation phase, treatment of osteoarthritis patients with physical and natural factors is approached to be based on the results obtained when the treatment is carried out in combination with other means.

Purpose of work. To increase the effectiveness of rehabilitation treatment, it is necessary to develop and substantiate coordinated complex rehabilitation methods based on a differentiated approach to patients with osteoarthritis. It also consists of a comparative study of the dynamics of indicators that improve the quality of life of patients after the recommended rehabilitation.

Materials and methods. In 2018-2021, **107** male and female **patients** (average age 50,7) who were treated with osteoarthritis in the rheumatology, traumatology and physiotherapy departments of the Bukhara regional multidisciplinary medical center were involved

in the research with their consent. Among them, 61.7% of patients were diagnosed with gonarthrosis and 38.3% were diagnosed with coxarthrosis.

General clinical, instrumental, functional and statistical methods of research and analysis were used to solve research tasks. The collected data were analyzed by medical statistical and mathematical methods.

Physiotherapy (electrophoresis, laser, magnetotherapy) as well as physical exercises (butterfly pose, joint mobility exercises) were performed in the main group of patients with OA. In the comparison group, only physiotherapeutic procedures were recommended. The nature of the recommended treatment and the method of execution were selected individually, taking into account the accompanying diseases of the patients. One course of treatment consisted of 15 exercises, which were conducted every day for 30-40 minutes. Treatment exercises were recommended from the 3rd day of treatment. Treatment exercises for osteoarthritis were carried out in an individual approach, depending on the nature of pain in the joints, while sitting and lying down, gradually increasing the range of motion. Sharp movements and exercises that cause severe pain are not performed. The main principle that the patient should follow when performing therapeutic exercises is the regularity and gradualness of the exercises. In each session, the patient's heart rate and breathing rate were taken into account. Heart rate during exercise and at rest was determined.

The results obtained. Patients who participated in the survey were divided into 2 groups in a representative manner. When they were analyzed according to the place of residence, the following results were found in the groups: in all groups, patients with osteoarthritis were more common among rural residents than urban residents (75.2% ; 74.7%). Wide spread of this pathology among the rural population, one of the risk factors of this disease can be attributed to the effect of excessive physical stress on their joints.

Table 1

Description of the severity of the disease in patients with osteoarthritis

Group	Diagnosis	Severity of OA (%)		
		I	II	III
research group	gonarthrosis	25.3%	43.7%	31.0%
	coxarthrosis	34.4%	43.7%	21.9%
control group	gonarthrosis	21.5%	46.4%	32.1%
	coxarthrosis	22.7%	45.5%	31.8%

The severity of the disease in the examined patients was analyzed depending on the area of the affected joint of osteoarthritis. In both of these groups, the II degree of the disease was observed relatively more. (Table 2).

According to the general analysis of comorbidities in patients with OA, obesity (39.4 ± 2.12 ; 38.9 ± 1.11), arterial hypertension (26.2 ± 0.04 ; 24.7 ± 0.06), diabetes (11.65 ± 0.03 ; 12.2 ± 1.09), osteochondrosis (22.3 ± 0.04 ; 22.6 ± 0.13), chronic gastritis (15.53 ± 0.04 ; 16.12 ± 1.18), chronic pancreatitis (5.83 ± 0.02 ; 4.17 ± 1.26), peptic ulcer disease (7.77 ± 0.03 ; 6.54 ± 0.25) was found in both groups.

As a result of carrying out rehabilitation methods in patients with osteoarthritis, the improvement of their condition was shown by the reduction of swelling of tissues around the joints ($p < 0.05$). Table 2 shows the dynamics of indicators in joints in patients with OA.

the dynamics of clinical indicators of patients in the main group and the comparison group receiving rehabilitation treatments for OA revealed significant differences in the clinical symptoms of the disease after the course.

Table 2

Changes in the joint

Group	I	II	I	II
Signs	<i>Before treatment</i>		<i>After treatment</i>	

movement is limited	3,17±2,11	3,42±1,36	0,67±2,51	2,26±2,67
cramps in the joint	0,95±1,31	0,83±1,74	0,33±1,42	0,72±1,53
deformation	2,37±0,13	2,30±1,09	1,29±1,25	1,95±1,01
swelling	0,97±2,58	0,94±1,26	0,19±2,34	0,69±2,72

Patients in the main group showed significant ($p < 0.05$) improvement in all clinical parameters, while patients in the comparison group showed no significant change in the studied parameters. In particular, a significant improvement in joint stiffness and swelling index was found in the observation group, which was not observed in patients in the comparison group.

Table 3

Dynamics of clinical indicators in patients with OA, in scores (before and after treatment)

Clinical signs	Group I	Group II
VASh scale	6.36±0.16*	5.23±0.32*
	1.84±0.11*	4.17±0.23*
Leken index	6.53±0.17*	7.27±0.27
	4.92±0.14*	6.7±0.23
Evening pain intensity	1.30 ±0.06*	1, 57±0.11
	0.86 ±0.05*	1.43 ±0.11
Morning sickness	1.23 ±0.05 *	1.40 ±0.09
	0.93±0.05*	1.23±0.09

* The difference between before and after treatment is $p < 0.05$

According to the indicators presented in Table 3, when comparing the results before and after the treatment in the main group, the level of reliability $p < 0.05$ was reduced in the intensity of pain in the joints according to the VASh

scale (from 6.36 ± 0.16 to 1.84 ± 0.11), improvement of the functional state of the joints according to the Leken index (from 6.53 ± 0.17 to 4.92 ± 0.14), evening pain intensity (from 1.30 ± 0.06 to 0.86 ± 0.05), morning numbness (from 1.23 ± 0.05 to 0.93 ± 0.05) appears to have changed positively. In the comparison group, only the indicators on the VASh scale have a reliability level of $p < 0.05$.

According to the X-ray examination of the knee joint of the patients in the main group, there are relatively more changes of the II degree, while according to the X-ray examinations of the patients in the comparison group, the signs of the II and III degrees give the same indicator.

As a result of the physiotherapeutic and therapeutic exercises recommended in the main group for patients with OA, the condition of patients improved positively. It was manifested by the reduction of swelling of the tissues around the joint and the reduction of pain, as a result of which the bending and writing movements of the joints changed significantly ($p < 0.05$) when examined by the goniometry method. The dynamics of movement changes in the joint were measured and compared with goniometry every 3, 6, 12 months.

Due to the fact that only physiotherapeutic procedures were recommended to the patients of the comparison group, it was observed that their changes were lower than the results of the first group of patients.

In patients with OA, the increase in joint range of motion was more pronounced in the main group than in the comparison group after a course of rehabilitation treatment. After 3, 6, 12 months, under the influence of the rehabilitation course, the amplitude of bending movements in the joint in the main group gave the following indicators on average: $2.04 \pm 1.2^\circ$; $7.35 \pm 1.4^\circ$; $15.67 \pm 1.2^\circ$ ($p < 0.05$). The indicators in the comparison group changed as follows: $1.67 \pm 2.8^\circ$; $3.17 \pm 2.8^\circ$; $3.97 \pm 2.7^\circ$. In patients, the amplitude of writing movements in the joint is $-0.66 \pm 0.6^\circ$; $-6.62 \pm 0.6^\circ$; $-11.71 \pm 0.5^\circ$ expressed indicators ($p < 0.05$). When we analyzed such indicators in the comparison group,

we got the following results: $-0.50 \pm 0.9^\circ$; $-1.60 \pm 1.0^\circ$; $-2.2 \pm 1.1^\circ$. The increase in the amplitude of joint movement in the patients of the main group was significantly different from the patients in the comparison group: $2.0 \pm 1.9^\circ$; $2.87 \pm 0.8^\circ$; $-1.81 \pm 2.1^\circ$; $7.73 \pm 0.8^\circ$; $-9.33 \pm 1.9^\circ$; $12.22 \pm 0.7^\circ$ ($p < 0.05$).

The feasibility of developing differentiated rehabilitation methods for patients with OA was assessed by a quality of life study. After treatment with physical factors and exercise, the quality of life of patients with OA was not observed to worsen on any scale.

Table 4

Dynamics of quality of life indicators in patients with osteoarthritis

Indicators	Main group		Comparison group	
	Before treatment	After treatment	Before treatment	After treatment
Physical activity	58.06 ± 1.88	68.64 ± 2.11	57.09 ± 2.07	65.2 ± 3.1
Representation of training with physical condition	22.66 ± 3.15	51.48 ± 3.45	23.6 ± 2.7	41.34 ± 2.54
Pain intensity	41.26 ± 1.74	57.77 ± 2.17	31.8 ± 2.2	40.74 ± 2.97
General health	47.54 ± 1.65	54.43 ± 1.82	43.9 ± 2.7	51.7 ± 2.01
Life activity	49.42 ± 1.84	69.47 ± 2.01	44.23 ± 2.81	63.76 ± 1.1
Social activities	60.69 ± 1.96	76.94 ± 2.04	48.22 ± 1.28	67.42 ± 1.8
Conditional emotional state	38.78 ± 3.82	65.53 ± 2.42	31.61 ± 2.77	53.41 ± 3.1
Mental health	56.48 ± 1.61	73.12 ± 1.97	51.69 ± 2.12	66.44 ± 2.24

The reliability of the differences in the average values of the studied parameters in comparison with the initial values is as follows: $p < 0.05$.

It was found that the quality of life of patients improved significantly in all scales. At the same time, a significant improvement in both physical and psychological quality of life indicators was found in patients with OA after a complex rehabilitation course. It is worth noting that the greatest dynamics in terms of physical component indicators were established in the life activity scales.

Summary. Therapeutic effect of complex rehabilitation methods in patients with significant decrease in joint pain and morning stiffness during rest and movement, increase in joint mobility, positive changes in psychophysiological state and quality of life, and in patients with osteoarthritis accompanied by hypertension, low mobility, and excess body weight. significant improvement of systemic hemodynamics was found. Taking into account the compatibility of the methods, the procedures given in the complex rehabilitation of patients with degenerative-dystrophic and inflammatory diseases of the joints, especially osteoarthrosis, have had a significant effect.

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